

DARK MATTER THEORY OVERVIEW

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OUTLINE

- dark matter: why / where / what?
- DM \Leftrightarrow neutrinos
 - sterile neutrino as DM
 - portals to dark sector: HNLs, pNGBs
 - Majoron as DM

WHY?

(EVIDENCE FOR DARK MATTER)

EVIDENCE FOR DARK MATTER

for a review, see, e.g., Cirelli, Strumia, JZ, 2406.01705

- evidence for dark matter comes from several different scales
- Mini: galaxies
 - rotation curves of spiral galaxies
- Midi: clusters of galaxies
 - weak gravitational lensing: the bullet cluster
- Maxi: the Universe
 - large scale structure formation
 - CMB acoustic peaks
 - indirectly also via Big Bang Nucleosynthesis
($n_{\text{baryon}}/n_{\gamma}$)

DARK MATTER

- note: proportions of DM vs. the rest evolves with z

Cirelli, Strumia, JZ, 2406.01705

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DARK MATTER PROPERTIES

- global fits to cosmological observations (LSS+CMB):
 - *cold non-interacting dark matter with Gaussian adiabatic perturbations*
- gravitational force dominates DM interactions at long (cosmological) distances
 - DM-neutrino interactions below $\sigma_\nu \lesssim 10^{-32} (M_{\text{DM}}/\text{GeV}) \text{ cm}^2$
 - DM-photon interactions below $\sigma_\gamma \lesssim \text{few } 10^{-33} (M_{\text{DM}}/\text{GeV}) \text{ cm}^2$
 - any other long range forces between DM $\sim 10^{-2} \times \text{gravity}$

WHERE?

(DARK MATTER DISTRIBUTION IN THE
GALAXY AND THE UNIVERSE)

DARK MATTER DISTRIBUTION

- DM undergoes gravitational collapse
 - on cosmic scales it forms filament like structures

Results from a full-sky
N-body DM simulation
(Potter et al., 1609.08621)

DARK MATTER DISTRIBUTION

- on galactic scales DM forms roughly spherical halos
 - these are composed from many smaller sub-halos

WHAT?

(DARK MATTER CANDIDATES)

CATALOGUE OF THE UNIVERSE

- dark matter candidates can have mass or radius anywhere in the white space

Cirelli, Strumia, JZ, 2406.01705

LARGE RANGE OF POSSIBILITIES

sterile neutrino

Cirelli, Strumia, JZ, 2406.01705

- three distinct regimes
 - for $M_{\text{DM}} \lesssim \mathcal{O}(\text{eV})$ behaves as classical field
 - heavier: DM behaves as collection of particles
 - well above M_{Pl} DM particles are macroscopic objects

PARTICLE DARK MATTER

DARK MATTER

• • • Needs confirmation • • •

PROPERTIES

$I(J^{PC})$	MASS	WIDTH	DECAY MODES	PRODUCTION
$?(???)$	$? \pm ?$	$? \pm ?$	STABLE ?	$\sigma(?? \rightarrow ??) = ?$

DARK MATTER DETECTION

Cirelli, Strumia, JZ, 2406.0170

GLOBAL EXPERIMENTAL EFFORT

Cirelli, Strumia, JZ, 2406.01705

-
- what does this have to do with neutrinos?
 - sterile neutrino as DM
 - neutrino portals to dark sectors
 - Majoron as DM

PARTICLE DARK MATTER

- a good DM candidate must satisfy
 - DM must be cold ($v \ll c$)
 - DM electric charge q must be zero or very small
 - xsec for scattering of DM on normal matter is smaller than a typical weak cross section: $\sigma \ll 1/m_Z^2$
 - xsec among two DM particles must be smaller than typical QCD xsec: $\sigma/M_{\text{DM}} \ll (\text{GeV}/M_{\text{DM}})/m_\pi^2$
 - DM particle must be stable ($\tau \gtrsim 10^{28} \text{ s}$)
- sterile neutrino fits the bill

STERILE NEUTRINO AS DM

- one minimal choice for DM: add to the SM an extra neutral Weyl fermion N
 - if no Z_2 symmetry then this is a decaying DM candidate

for a review see, e.g., [Drewes et al., 1602.04816](#)

$$\mathcal{L} = \mathcal{L}_{\text{SM}} + \bar{N}i\not{\partial}N + \left(M\frac{N^2}{2} + yNLH + \text{h.c.} \right)$$

- interactions from N - ν_{SM} mixing $\theta = yv/M \ll 1$
 - $N \rightarrow 3\nu$ dominant decay channel
 - $N \rightarrow \nu\gamma$ decay leads to most stringent constraints
- for DM relevant the $M_{\text{DM}} \sim \mathcal{O}(\text{keV})$ mass regime

STERILE NEUTRINO AS DM

Cirelli, Strumia, JZ, 2406.01705

NON-DECAYING STERILE N

- imposing Z_2 symmetry $N_i \rightarrow -N_i$ would ensure lightest N to be stable

- needs extra fields to be able to write down interactions with the SM

Ma, [hep-ph/0601225](#)

- scotogenic model: extra Higgs double η

$$\mathcal{L} \supset y \bar{L} \eta N$$

- neutrino masses zero at tree level
 - only generated at one loop level

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SCOTOGENIC DM

Sahoo et al, 2601.00436

- lightest $N_i (= N_1)$ can be DM
 - while satisfying other constraints, including neutrino mass spectra
- correct relic abundance
 - freeze-out: N_1 mass $M_{\text{DM}} \sim 0.1 - 1 \text{ TeV}$
 - freeze-in: N_1 can be lighter, $M_{\text{DM}} \sim \text{GeV}$ possible
- most promising signature: displaced vertices at LHC

DM

Sahoo et al, 2601.00436

nts, including

0.1 – 1 TeV

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2601.00436

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NEUTRINO PORTALS TO DARK SECTOR

- just a few renormalizable or dim-5 operators (portals) to dark sector
- neutrinos relevant for two
 - HNLs
 - pNGBs (ALPs) that preferentially couple to neutrinos
 - example: Majoron

Portal	Interactions
Dark Photon, A'_μ	$-\epsilon F'_{\mu\nu} B^{\mu\nu}$
Dark Higgs, S	$(\mu S + \lambda S^2) H^\dagger H$
Heavy Neutral Lepton, N	$y_N L H N$
Axion-like pseudo scalar, a	$a F \tilde{F} / f_a, a G \tilde{G} / f_a, (\bar{\psi} \gamma^\mu \gamma_5 \psi) \partial_\mu a / f_a$

HEAVY NEUTRAL LEPTONS

for a review see, e.g., Abullahi et al, 2203.08039
 see also talk by Jacobo López-Pavón

- common limit: assume mixing with just one of ν_e, ν_μ or ν_τ

(semi-)leptonic decays

beam dump exp.

collider searches + EWPT

ENHANCED NEUTRINO POLARIZABILITY

see talk by M. Tamaro

- a light pNGB that couples to both neutrinos and photons

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{int}} = -\frac{g_\gamma}{4} \phi F_{\mu\nu} \tilde{F}^{\mu\nu} + \frac{1}{2} c_\nu^{ij} \phi \bar{\nu}_i^c P_L \nu_j + \text{h.c.},$$

- at low energies it induces neutrino polarizability operators

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{pol.}} = \frac{1}{2} \alpha_{\nu,ij} (\bar{\nu}_i^c P_L \nu_j) F_{\mu\nu} F^{\mu\nu} + \frac{1}{2} \tilde{\alpha}_{\nu,ij} (\bar{\nu}_i^c P_L \nu_j) F_{\mu\nu} \tilde{F}^{\mu\nu}$$

$$\tilde{\alpha}_{\nu,ij} = c_\nu^{ij} \frac{g_\gamma}{4m_\phi^2}.$$

- enhanced by small ϕ mass
- can be discovered at DUNE from 1EM and 2EM signatures

RINO PHY

see talk by M. Tammaro

measurability

operators

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{pol.}} = \frac{1}{2} \alpha_{\nu,ij} (\bar{\nu}_i^c P_L \nu_j) F_{\mu\nu} F^{\mu\nu} + \frac{1}{2} \tilde{\alpha}_{\nu,ij} (\bar{\nu}_i^c P_L \nu_j) F_{\mu\nu} \tilde{F}^{\mu\nu}$$

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MAJORON AS DARK MATTER

- Majoron is a pNGB of spontaneously broken lepton number
 - minimal singlet model

see, e.g. Heeck, Patel, 1909.02029

$$\mathcal{L} = -\bar{L}yN_R H - \frac{1}{2}\bar{N}_R^c \lambda N_R \sigma + \text{h.c.} - V(H, \sigma), \quad \sigma = (f + \sigma^0 + iJ)/\sqrt{2}$$

- Majoron mass a free parameter: $m_J^2 J^2$ breaks $U(1)_L$
- can be DM, can be long lived on cosmological time-scales
- different production mechanisms in different mass regimes

$$\Gamma(J \rightarrow \nu\nu) \sim \frac{1}{400 \text{ Gyr}} \left(\frac{m_J}{\text{MeV}}\right) \left(\frac{10^9 \text{ GeV}}{f}\right)^2$$

- freeze-in for $m_J \sim \mathcal{O}(\text{MeV})$
 - for $m_J \sim \mathcal{O}(\text{keV})$ need to ensure cold enough
 - misalignment for $m_J \sim \mathcal{O}(\text{eV})$
- exp. signatures from $J \rightarrow 2\nu, J \rightarrow 2\gamma$
 - at loop level also couplings to charged leptons, can search from $\mu \rightarrow eJ$

Frigerio, Hambye, Masso, 1107.4564

see, e.g. Heeck, 1809.09413

Kusenko et al, 2506.23401

MAJ

- Majoron
- mini
- Majoron
- can be D
- lived on
- time-sca
- different

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MANY OTHER TOPICS

- time dependent neutrino masses from couplings to ultra-light DM

$$(\hat{m}_\nu)_{ij} = m_i \delta_{ij} + \hat{y}_{ij} \phi,$$

$$\phi = \phi_0 \sin(m_\phi(t - t_0))$$

Berlin, 1608.01307

Losada et al, 2302.00005

- can be searched for at neutrino oscillation experiments
- bounds on dark matter neutrino interactions Chauhan et al, 2505.03882
 - SN1987A+diffuse SN ν 's : $\sigma_{\text{DM}-\nu}/M_{\text{DM}} \lesssim 10^{-24} \text{ cm}^2/\text{GeV}$
for $M \gtrsim 1 \text{ GeV}$ see also Babu et al, 2512.25035
- DM annihilations in the sun to neutrinos
 - important bound on DM scattering rates
- neutrino detectors searching for (boosted) DM Necib et al, 1610.03486
- neutrino physics with dark matter detectors
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Direct Detection constraints on SI scattering

- time DM
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- SN
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Necib et al, 1610.03486

CONCLUSIONS

- evidence for dark matter comes from galactic to cosmic scales
- in many instances neutrinos can be a window to dark matter sector
- sterile neutrino DM, Majoron, neutrino portal to dark sectors, ...

BACKUP SLIDES

DARK MATTER PROPERTIES

- global fits to cosmological observations (LSS+CMB):
 - cold non-interacting dark matter with Gaussian adiabatic perturbations
 - bounds on DM not being cold ideal gas but more complicated dark fluid are at $\mathcal{O}(10^{-3})$ level
 - nonzero sound speed v_s (making DM not cold)
 - nonzero viscosity (making DM interacting)
 - modified equation of state $w = p/\rho = 0$ (DM no longer behaving as nonrelativistic matter)

NEUTRINO AS DARK MATTER

- SM neutrino could be a DM candidate
 - is electrically neutral, only weakly-interacting, stable, has non-zero mass
 - cosmological DM density would be reproduced if
$$\sum_{\nu} m_{\nu} \approx 11 \text{ eV}$$
- this possibility excluded for several reasons
 - would be warm dark matter
 - neutrinos must be lighter, $m_{\nu} \lesssim \text{eV}$ (KATRIN, $0\nu 2\beta$ decay)
 - bounds from matter clustering in cosmology imply
$$\sum_{\nu} m_{\nu} \lesssim \text{few } 0.1 \text{ eV}$$

SOME HISTORIC DM CANDIDATES

Cirelli, Strumia, JZ, 2406.01705

Candidate	Date	Reference(s)
Primordial BH	1966, 1971	Zeldovich & Novikov, Hawking [86]
MACHOs	1981, 1986	Petrou; Paczynski [83]
Gravitinos	1981, 1982	Fayet; Witten; Pagel & Primack [100]
Axions	1983	Preskill, Wise & Wilczek [101]
Neutralinos	1984	Ellis et al. [102]
Strangelets	1984	Witten; Fahri & Jaffe [103]
Q-balls	1984	Witten [104]
Extra-dimensional DM	1984	Kolb & Slansky; Servant & Tait [105]
WIMPs	1985	Steigman & Turner [106]
Sterile neutrinos	1993	Dodelson & Widrow [107]
Fuzzy DM	2000	Hu, Barkana & Gruzinov [108]
Sub-GeV DM	2003	Boehm, Fayet et al. [109]

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$$\Omega_J h^2 \simeq 0.12 \left(\frac{m_J}{25 \text{ eV}}\right)^{1/2} \left(\frac{F_J \theta_i}{2.7 \times 10^{11} \text{ GeV}}\right)^2$$

